

**PARTITION INEQUALITIES AND APPLICATIONS TO
SUM-PRODUCT CONJECTURES OF KANADE-RUSSELL**

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Abstract

We consider differences of one- and two-variable finite products and provide combinatorial proofs of the nonnegativity of certain coefficients. Since the products may be interpreted as generating functions for certain integer partitions, this amounts to showing a partition inequality. This extends results due to Berkovich-Garvan and McLaughlin. We then apply the first inequality and Andrews' Anti-telescoping Method to give a solution to an "Ehrenpreis Problem" for recently conjectured sum-product identities of Kanade-Russell. That is, we provide significant further evidence for Kanade-Russell's conjectures by showing nonnegativity of coefficients in differences of product-sides as Andrews-Baxter and Kadell did for the product sides of the Rogers-Ramanujan identities.

1. Introduction

A *partition* λ of an integer n is a multi-set of positive integers $\{\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_\ell\}$, whose *parts* satisfy

$$\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_\ell \geq 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{j=1}^{\ell} \lambda_j = n.$$

We will often use *frequency notation* to refer to a partition, where $(r^{m_r}, \dots, 2^{m_2}, 1^{m_1})$ represents the partition in which the part i occurs m_i times for $1 \leq i \leq r$.

Visually, a partition λ may be represented by its *Ferrer's diagram*, in which parts are displayed as rows of dots. For example, the Ferrer's diagram of the partition $(5, 3, 2^2)$ is the array below.

For two q -series $f(q) = \sum_{n \geq 0} a_n q^n$ and $g(q) = \sum_{n \geq 0} b_n q^n$, we write $f(q) \succeq g(q)$ if $a_n \geq b_n$ for all n . If $f(q) \succeq 0$, we will say that f is a *nonnegative series*.

We will use the standard q -Pochhammer symbol,

$$(a; q)_n := \prod_{j=0}^{n-1} (1 - aq^j), \quad (a; q)_\infty := \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (a; q)_n, \quad \text{and}$$

$$(a_1, \dots, a_r; q)_n := (a_1; q)_n \cdots (a_r; q)_n.$$

By convention, an empty product equals 1.

The study of the type of partition inequality we consider began at the 1987 A.M.S. Institute on Theta Functions with a question of Leon Ehrenpreis about the Rogers-Ramanujan Identities ([3], Cor. 7.6 and Cor. 7.7):

$$\mathcal{RR}_1 : \sum_{n \geq 0} \frac{q^{n^2}}{(q; q)_n} = \frac{1}{(q, q^4; q^5)_\infty},$$

$$\mathcal{RR}_2 : \sum_{n \geq 0} \frac{q^{n^2+n}}{(q; q)_n} = \frac{1}{(q^2, q^3; q^5)_\infty}.$$

The identity \mathcal{RR}_1 may be interpreted as an equality of certain partition generating functions, giving that the number of partitions of n such that the gap between successive parts is at least 2 equals the number of partitions of n into parts congruent to $\pm 1 \pmod{5}$. Similarly, \mathcal{RR}_2 gives that the number of partitions of n such that the gap between successive parts is at least 2 and 1 does not occur as a part equals the number of partitions of n into parts congruent to $\pm 2 \pmod{5}$. Thus, both combinatorially and algebraically, it is easy to see that

$$\sum_{n \geq 0} \frac{q^{n^2}}{(q; q)_n} - \sum_{n \geq 0} \frac{q^{n^2+n}}{(q; q)_n} \succeq 0.$$

Therefore, it also holds that

$$\frac{1}{(q, q^4; q^5)_\infty} - \frac{1}{(q^2, q^3; q^5)_\infty} \succeq 0. \tag{1}$$

Ehrenpreis' Problem was to provide a proof of (1) that did not reference the (heavy-handed and quite nontrivial) Rogers-Ramanujan identities.

Solutions to Ehrenpreis' Problem have been given in various ways. In the course of proving (1), Andrews-Baxter [2] were led to a new "motivated" proof of the Rogers-Ramanujan Identities themselves. A direct combinatorial proof of (1) was provided by Kadell [8], who constructed an injection from the set of partitions of n with parts congruent to $\pm 2 \pmod{5}$ to those with parts congruent to $\pm 1 \pmod{5}$. Later, Andrews developed the Anti-telescoping Method for showing positivity in differences of products like (1) [1]. This method was used by Berkovich-Grizzell in [5] to prove infinite classes of partition inequalities, such as the following.

Theorem (Theorem 1.2 of [5]). For any octuple of positive integers (L, m, x, y, z, r, s, u) ,

$$\frac{1}{(q^x, q^y, q^z, q^{rx+sy+uz}, q^m)_L} - \frac{1}{(q^{rx}, q^{sy}, q^{uz}, q^{x+y+z}, q^m)_L} \succeq 0.$$

In [4], Berkovich-Garvan generalized (1) to an arbitrary modulus as follows.

Theorem (Theorem 5.3 of [4]). Suppose $L \geq 1$ and $1 \leq r < \frac{M}{2}$. Then

$$\frac{1}{(q, q^{M-1}; q^M)_L} - \frac{1}{(q^r, q^{M-r}; q^M)_L} \succeq 0$$

if and only if $r \nmid (M - r)$.

One can apply Berkovich-Garvan’s result to solve similar “Ehrenpreis Problems” for Kanade-Russell’s “mod 9 identities” in [10].

The first result in this paper extends the above in a way that is independent of the modulus. We will use this in Section 3 to solve an “Ehrenpreis Problem” for conjectural product-sum identities of Kanade-Russell in [11].

Theorem 1. Let a, b, c and M be integers satisfying $1 < a < b < c$ and $1 + c = a + b$. Then if $a \nmid b$,

$$\frac{1}{(q, q^c; q^M)_L} - \frac{1}{(q^a, q^b; q^M)_L} \succeq 0 \quad \text{for any } L \geq 0.$$

Note that we do not necessarily assume $a, b, c \leq M$. Translated into a partition inequality, Theorem 1.1 says that there are more partitions of n into parts of the forms $Mj + 1$ and $Mj + c$ than there are partitions of n into parts of the forms $Mj + a$ and $Mj + b$, where throughout $1 \leq j \leq L$.

Partition inequalities with a fixed number of parts were considered by McLaughlin in [13]. Answering two of McLaughlin’s questions, we give combinatorial proofs of finite analogues of Theorems 7 and 8 from [13].

Theorem 2. Let a, b and M be integers satisfying $1 \leq a < b < \frac{M}{2}$ and $\gcd(b, M) = 1$. Define $c(m, n)$ by

$$\frac{1}{(zq^a, zq^{M-a}; q^M)_L(1 - q^{LM+a})} - \frac{1}{(zq^b, zq^{M-b}; q^M)_L} =: \sum_{m, n \geq 0} c(m, n)z^m q^n.$$

Then for any $L, n \geq 0$, we have $c(m, nM) \geq 0$. If in addition M is even and a is odd, then we also have $c(m, nM + \frac{M}{2}) \geq 0$ for every $n \geq 0$.

Note that we do not necessarily make the assumption $\gcd(a, M) = 1$ that is in [13]. While these partition inequalities hold only for n in certain residue classes (mod M), Theorem 2 is a strengthening of Theorem 1 for these n . The following is a distinct parts analogue.

Theorem 3. Let a, b and M be integers satisfying $1 \leq a < b < \frac{M}{2}$ and $\gcd(b, M) = 1$.

1. Define $d(m, n)$ by

$$(-zq^a, -zq^{M-a}; q^M)_L (1 + zq^{LM+a}) - (-zq^b, -zq^{M-b}; q^M)_L =: \sum_{m, n \geq 0} d(m, n) z^m q^n.$$

Then for any $L, n \geq 0$, we have $d(m, nM) \geq 0$. If in addition M is even and a is odd, then we also have $d(m, nM + \frac{M}{2}) \geq 0$ for every $n \geq 0$.

Remark. Taking the limit as $L \rightarrow \infty$ in Theorems 2 and 3 recovers McLaughlin’s original partition inequalities.

In Section 2, we begin by reviewing the M -modular diagram of a partition. Then we provide combinatorial proofs of Theorems 1-3. In Section 3, we apply Theorem 1 and Andrews’ Method of Anti-Telescoping (see [1]) to give a solution to an “Ehrenpreis Problem” for recently conjectured sum-product identities of Kanade-Russell [11]. Our concluding remarks in Section 4 ask for Andrews-Baxter style “motivated proofs” of these conjectured identities.

2. Combinatorial Proofs of Theorems 1-3

2.1. Notation

The M -modular diagram of a partition $\lambda = \{\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_\ell\}$ is a modification of the Ferrer’s diagram, wherein each λ_j is first written as $Mq + r$ for $0 \leq r < M$, and then is represented as a row of q M ’s and a single r at the end of the row. These r ’s we will refer to as *ends* or *r-ends*. For example, the 10-modular diagram of $\lambda = (53^2, 46, 36, 16, 11, 1)$ has three 6-ends, two 3-ends and two 1-ends:

We will also speak of *attaching* and *removing* a column from an M -modular diagram. These operations are best defined with an example:

- Case 1. For the $k - \ell$ excess a 's, $(a) \mapsto (1^a)$.
- Case 2. For the $\ell - k$ excess b 's, $(b) \mapsto (1^b)$.
- Case 3. For all but the last two excess b 's, $(b) \mapsto (1^b)$. For the last two b 's, $(b^2) \mapsto (1^{b-a+1}, c)$.

Note that in Case 3 there are at least two excess b 's, for if not, $\frac{a}{d} = 1$ and then $a \mid b$, a contradiction. Also, by hypothesis, $b > \frac{c}{2}$, so that $2b > c$.

Let $(1^{\nu_1}, c^{\nu_c})$ be a partition in the image of φ_1 . The cases are separated as follows:

- Case 1. $a \mid (\nu_1 - \nu_c)$,
- Case 2. $a \nmid (\nu_1 - \nu_c)$ and $b \mid (\nu_1 - \nu_c)$,
- Case 3. $\nu_1 - \nu_c \equiv -b \pmod{a}$ and $\nu_1 - \nu_c \equiv -a \pmod{b}$.

This concludes the proof for $L = 1$.

Now let $L \geq 2$. Again we define an injection

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_L : \{ \lambda \vdash n : \lambda_j \in \{a, b, \dots, LM + a, LM + b\} \} \\ \hookrightarrow \{ \lambda \vdash n : \lambda_j \in \{1, c, \dots, LM + 1, LM + c\} \}. \end{aligned}$$

Let λ be a partition in the left set. Then λ consists of the triple

$$(\lambda_{(a)}, \lambda_{(b)}, (a^k, b^\ell)),$$

where $\lambda_{(a)}$ is the M -modular diagram obtained by subtracting a from every part of the form $Mj + a$; $\lambda_{(b)}$ is defined similarly. We apply φ_1 to (a^k, b^ℓ) and reattach the 1-ends and c -ends based on the case into which (a^k, b^ℓ) falls.

Case 1: $k \geq \ell$. Attach the 1-ends to $\lambda_{(a)}$ and the c -ends to $\lambda_{(b)}$. The map φ_1 guarantees exactly $\#\lambda_{(b)}$ c -ends. Likewise, there are at least as many 1-ends as there are parts of $\lambda_{(a)}$; any excess 1's are attached as parts to $\lambda_{(a)}$. The required image of λ is then the union of these two partitions.

Cases 2 and 3: $\ell > k$. Attach the 1-ends to $\lambda_{(b)}$ and the c -ends to $\lambda_{(a)}$ as before. φ_1 guarantees at least $\#\lambda_{(a)}$ c -ends. In Case 2 we are guaranteed at least $\#\lambda_{(a)}$ 1-ends because $b > 1$ implies

$$k + b(\ell - k) > \ell.$$

In Case 3, $\frac{a}{d} > 1$ implies $\ell - k > 1$, so

$$k + 1 + b(\ell - k - 1) - a = \ell + (b - 1)(\ell - k - 1) - a \geq \ell,$$

and we are guaranteed at least $\#\lambda_{(a)}$ 1-ends.

Given the image of λ , we may clearly recover $\lambda_{(a)}$ and $\lambda_{(b)}$ based on its 1-ends and c -ends and the fact that φ_1 is an injection. Thus, φ_L is an injection. \square

Remark. The condition $a \nmid b$ in Theorem 1 is necessary to avoid cases like

$$\frac{1}{(q, q^5; q^6)_L} - \frac{1}{(q^2, q^4; q^6)_L},$$

in which the coefficient of q^4 is -1 .

Remark. If we had copied the proof of Theorem 5.1 in [4] exactly, then the conditions “ $\frac{a}{d} \mid$ ” and “ $\frac{a}{d} \nmid$ ” would be replaced by “ $a \mid$ ” and “ $a \nmid$ ”. But this is not an injection because Case 2 is only correctly separated from the other two when $\gcd(a, b) = 1$. For example, this direct version of Berkovich-Garvan’s map gives:

$$\begin{cases} 4^7, 6^4 \\ 4^4, 6^6 \end{cases} \longrightarrow (1^{16}, 9^4), \quad \text{instead of our} \quad \begin{cases} 4^7, 6^4 \\ 4^4, 6^6 \end{cases} \longrightarrow \begin{cases} 1^{16}, 9^4 \\ 1^7, 9^5 \end{cases}.$$

In the first example, the partitions fall into cases 1 and 2. The second example corrects the overlap and places the partitions into cases 1 and 3.

We demonstrate the injection of Theorem 1 with an example.

Example 1. Here, $(n, M, L, a, b, c) = (52, 10, 2, 4, 6, 9)$. Numbers above arrows indicate the case into which a pre-image falls.

$16^3, 4$	$\xrightarrow{3}$	$11^3, 9^2, 1$		$14^2, 6^4$	$\xrightarrow{3}$	$19^2, 9, 1^5$
$16^2, 14, 6$	$\xrightarrow{3}$	$19, 11^2, 9, 1^2$		$14^2, 6^2, 4^3$	$\xrightarrow{1}$	$11^2, 9^2, 1^{12}$
$16^2, 6^2, 4^2$	$\xrightarrow{3}$	$11^2, 9^3, 1^3$		$14^2, 4^6$	$\xrightarrow{1}$	$11^2, 1^{30}$
$16^2, 4^5$	$\xrightarrow{1}$	$19^2, 1^{14}$		$14, 6^5, 4^2$	$\xrightarrow{3}$	$19, 9^3, 1^6$
$16, 14^2, 4^2$	$\xrightarrow{1}$	$19, 11^2, 1^{11}$		$14, 6^3, 4^5$	$\xrightarrow{1}$	$11, 9^3, 1^{14}$
$16, 14, 6^3, 4$	$\xrightarrow{3}$	$19, 11, 9^2, 1^4$		$14, 6, 4^8$	$\xrightarrow{1}$	$11, 9, 1^{32}$
$16, 14, 6, 4^4$	$\xrightarrow{1}$	$19, 11, 9, 1^{13}$		$6^8, 4$	$\xrightarrow{2}$	$9, 1^{43}$
$16, 6^6$	$\xrightarrow{2}$	$11, 1^{41}$		$6^6, 4^4$	$\xrightarrow{3}$	$9^5, 1^7$
$16, 6^4, 4^3$	$\xrightarrow{3}$	$11, 9^4, 1^5$		$6^4, 4^7$	$\xrightarrow{1}$	$9^4, 1^{16}$
$16, 6^2, 4^6$	$\xrightarrow{1}$	$19, 9^2, 1^{15}$		$6^2, 4^{10}$	$\xrightarrow{1}$	$9^2, 1^{34}$
$16, 4^9$	$\xrightarrow{1}$	$19, 1^{33}$		4^{13}	$\xrightarrow{1}$	1^{52}
$14^3, 6, 4$	$\xrightarrow{1}$	$11^3, 9, 1^{10}$				

2.3. Proofs of Theorems 2 and 3

We begin by recalling the main steps in McLaughlin’s proof of Theorem 7 from [13]; our proof is based on a combinatorial reading. First, Cauchy’s Theorem ([3], Th. 2.1) is used with some algebraic manipulation to write, for fixed m ,

$$\sum_{n \geq 0} c(m, n)q^n = \sum_{\substack{0 \leq k < \frac{m}{2} \\ M | m - 2k}} \frac{q^{kM}}{(q^M; q^M)_{m-k} (q^M; q^M)_k} \times \left(q^{a(m-2k)} + q^{(M-a)(m-2k)} - q^{b(m-2k)} - q^{(M-b)(m-2k)} \right).$$

It then happens that the factor in parentheses is equal to

$$q^{a(m-2k)} \left(1 - q^{(b-a)(m-2k)} \right) \left(1 - q^{(M-b-a)(m-2k)} \right).$$

But the conditions on a, b and M that lead to the condition $M \mid (m - 2k)$ in the sum imply that both factors above are canceled in $\frac{1}{(q^M; q^M)_{m-k}}$. This gives nonnegativity.

The key steps in the proof are the decomposition of the sum over k and the nonnegativity of

$$\frac{(1 - q^r)(1 - q^s)}{(q; q)_n} \quad \text{for } 1 \leq r < s \leq n.$$

Both of these have simple combinatorial explanations, which we employ with M -modular diagrams to piece together a proof of Theorem 2. Our proof naturally leads to the finite versions with any $L \geq 1$ instead of ∞ . The proof of Theorem 3 is then a slight modification.

Proof of Theorem 2. Let $\mathcal{P}(n, m, j, A)$ denote the set of partitions of n into m parts congruent to $\pm j$ modulo M such that the largest part is at most A . (We have suppressed the modulus M from the notation.) Let $\mathcal{P}_k(n, m, j, A)$ be the subset of partitions $\lambda \in \mathcal{P}(n, m, j, A)$ with either $\nu_j(\lambda) = k$ or $\nu_{M-j}(\lambda) = k$.

Clearly, we have the disjoint union $\mathcal{P}(n, m, j, A) = \bigsqcup_{0 \leq k \leq \frac{m}{2}} \mathcal{P}_k(n, m, j, A)$. Thus, to show

$$\mathcal{P}(nM, m, b, LM - b) \hookrightarrow \mathcal{P}(nM, m, a, LM + a),$$

we may provide injections

$$\varphi_k : \mathcal{P}_k(nM, m, b, LM - b) \hookrightarrow \mathcal{P}_k(nM, m, a, LM + a)$$

for each $k \in [0, \frac{m}{2}]$.

Each $\lambda \in \mathcal{P}(nM, m, b, LM - b)$ consists of a triple

$$(\lambda_{(b)}, \lambda_{(M-b)}, (b^{\nu_b}, (M - b)^{\nu_{M-b}})),$$

where $\lambda_{(b)}$ is the M -modular diagram with ν_b nonnegative parts created by removing the b -ends. The M -modular diagram $\lambda_{(M-b)}$ is defined analogously by removing the $(M - b)$ -ends.

When $k = \frac{m}{2}$, we simply map

$$\varphi_{\frac{m}{2}}(\lambda_{(b)}, \lambda_{(M-b)}, (b^{\frac{m}{2}}, (M - b)^{\frac{m}{2}})) := (\lambda_{(b)}, \lambda_{(M-b)}, (a^{\frac{m}{2}}, (M - a)^{\frac{m}{2}})).$$

The required partition is then obtained by reattaching the a -ends to $\lambda_{(b)}$ and reattaching the $(M - a)$ -ends to $\lambda_{(M-b)}$.

Now assume $k < \frac{m}{2}$. Note that

$$0 \equiv nM \equiv b\nu_b(\lambda) - b\nu_{M-b}(\lambda) \pmod{M}, \tag{2}$$

which implies $\nu_b(\lambda) - \nu_{M-b}(\lambda) \equiv 0 \pmod{M}$ because $\gcd(b, M) = 1$. Thus, we assume without loss of generality that $M \mid (m - 2k)$.

Let $y := \frac{(b-a)(m-2k)}{M}$ and $z := \frac{(M-b-a)(m-2k)}{M}$. These are positive integers.

Case 1: $\nu_{M-b}(\lambda) = k$. There are k pairs of $(b, M - b)$ and $m - 2k$ excess b 's. We map

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_k(\lambda_{(b)}, \lambda_{(M-b)}, (b^{m-k}, (M - b)^k)) &:= \left(\lambda_{(b)} \cup \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} M \\ \vdots \\ M \end{bmatrix}}_{y \text{ rows}}, \lambda_{(M-b)}, (a^{m-k}, (M - a)^k) \right) \\ &=: (\lambda'_{(b)}, \lambda_{(M-b)}, (a^{m-k}, (M - a)^k)). \end{aligned}$$

Here $\lambda'_{(b)}$ is the M -modular diagram formed by attaching the above column to $\lambda_{(b)}$. Note that $a < b < M$ implies $0 < y < m - k$, so that $\lambda'_{(b)}$ is still an M -modular diagram with $m - k$ nonnegative parts.

To obtain the required partition, attach the a -ends to $\lambda'_{(b)}$ and the $(M - a)$ -ends to $\lambda_{(M-b)}$. It is evident that there are m parts. Size is preserved, as

$$\begin{aligned} &|\lambda'_{(b)}| + |\lambda_{(M-b)}| + (m - k)a + k(M - a) \\ &= |\lambda_{(b)}| + My + |\lambda_{(M-b)}| + a(m - 2k) + kM \\ &= |\lambda_{(b)}| + (b - a)(m - 2k) + |\lambda_{(M-b)}| + a(m - 2k) + kM \\ &= |\lambda_{(b)}| + |\lambda_{(M-b)}| + b(m - 2k) + kM \\ &= |\lambda|. \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, it is clear that the operations are reversible, so that, within Case 1, φ_k is an injection.

Case 2a: $\nu_b(\lambda) = k$ and $\lambda_{(M-b)}$ does not contain a column of height y .¹ There are k pairs of $(b, M - b)$ and $m - 2k$ excess $(M - b)$'s. We map

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_k(\lambda_{(b)}, \lambda_{(M-b)}, (b^k, (M - b)^{m-k})) &:= \left(\lambda_{(b)}, \lambda_{(M-b)} \cup \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} M \\ \vdots \\ M \end{bmatrix}}_{z \text{ rows}}, (a^{m-k}, (M - a)^k) \right) \\ &=: (\lambda_{(b)}, \lambda'_{(M-b)}, (a^{m-k}, (M - a)^k)), \end{aligned}$$

where $\lambda'_{(M-b)}$ is defined by attaching the above column. Note again that $b, a < \frac{M}{2}$ implies $0 < z < m - k$, so that $\lambda'_{(M-b)}$ is still an M -modular diagram with $m - k$ nonnegative parts. Furthermore, $b - a \neq M - b - a$, so $\lambda'_{(M-b)}$ still does not contain a column of height y .

To obtain the required partition, attach the a -ends to $\lambda'_{(M-b)}$ and the $(M - a)$ -ends to $\lambda_{(b)}$. It is evident that there are m parts. Size is preserved, as

$$\begin{aligned} &|\lambda_{(b)}| + |\lambda'_{(M-b)}| + (m - k)a + k(M - a) \\ &= |\lambda_{(b)}| + |\lambda_{(M-b)}| + Mz + a(m - 2k) + kM \\ &= |\lambda_{(b)}| + |\lambda_{(M-b)}| + (M - b - a)(m - 2k) + a(m - 2k) + kM \\ &= |\lambda_{(b)}| + |\lambda_{(M-b)}| + (M - b)(m - 2k) + kM \\ &= |\lambda|. \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, it is clear that the operations are reversible, so that, within Case 2a, φ_k is an injection.

Case 2b: $\nu_b(\lambda) = k$ and $\lambda_{(M-b)}$ contains a column of height y .² In this case we send

$$\begin{aligned} (\lambda_{(b)}, \lambda_{(M-b)}, (b^k, (M - b)^{m-k})) &\mapsto \left(\lambda_{(b)}, \lambda_{(M-b)} \setminus \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} M \\ \vdots \\ M \end{bmatrix}}_{y \text{ rows}}, (a^k, (M - a)^{m-k}) \right) \\ &=: (\lambda_{(b)}, \lambda'_{(M-b)}, (a^k, (M - a)^{m-k})), \end{aligned}$$

where $\lambda'_{(M-b)}$ is defined by removing the above column. As before, we still may consider $\lambda'_{(M-b)}$ an M -modular diagram with $m - k$ nonnegative parts.

¹Or equivalently, the y -th part of $\lambda_{(M-b)}$ equals the $(y + 1)$ -st part.

²Or equivalently, the y -th part of $\lambda_{(M-b)}$ is strictly greater than the $(y + 1)$ -st part.

To obtain the required partition, attach the a -ends to $\lambda_{(b)}$ and the $(M - a)$ -ends to $\lambda'_{(M-b)}$. It is evident that there are m parts. Size is preserved, as

$$\begin{aligned} & |\lambda_{(b)}| + |\lambda'_{(M-b)}| + ka + (m - k)(M - a) \\ &= |\lambda_{(b)}| + |\lambda_{(M-b)}| - My + kM + (M - a)(m - 2k) \\ &= |\lambda_{(b)}| + |\lambda_{(M-b)}| - (b - a)(m - 2k) + kM + (M - a)(m - 2k) \\ &= |\lambda_{(b)}| + |\lambda_{(M-b)}| + (M - b)(m - 2k) + kM \\ &= |\lambda|. \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, it is clear that the operations are reversible, so that, within Case 2b, φ_k is an injection.

Let $(\lambda_{(a)}, \lambda_{(M-a)}, a^{\nu_a}, (M - a)^{\nu_{M-a}})$ lie in the image of φ_k . Then cases are separated as follows.

- Case 1: $\nu_a > \nu_{M-a}$ and $\lambda_{(a)}$ contains a column of height y .
- Case 2a: $\nu_a > \nu_{M-a}$ and $\lambda_{(a)}$ does not contain a column of height y .
- Case 2b: $\nu_a < \nu_{M-a}$.

Finally, note that in each case φ_k adds at most M to the largest part of what becomes $\lambda_{(a)}$, so indeed φ_k maps $\mathcal{P}_k(nM, m, b, LM - b)$ into $\mathcal{P}_k(nM, m, a, LM + a)$ as required. This completes the proof of the first statement.

When M is even and a is odd, we can use exactly the same injections, assuming because of (2) that $m - 2k \equiv \frac{M}{2} \pmod{M}$. We note that $\gcd(b, M) = 1$ implies that b is also odd, so y and z are still integers. \square

Remark. We note that the extra factor $\frac{1}{(1 - q^{LM+a})}$ in the left term of Theorem 2 is necessary. For example, in

$$\frac{1}{(zq^2, zq^5; q^7)_2} - \frac{1}{(zq^3, zq^4; q^7)_2},$$

the coefficients of z^7q^{70} , $z^{13}q^{70}$, $z^{16}q^{70}$, and $z^{18}q^{70}$ are all negative.

The proof of Theorem 3 is similar, but now cases are determined by columns that occur twice.

Proof of Theorem 3. We define injections φ'_k to be the same as φ_k , except that in Cases 2a and 2b we condition on whether or not a partition contains *two* columns of height y . This ensures that φ'_k preserves distinct parts partitions:

Case 1: Note that $\lambda_{(b)}$ is a distinct parts partition into $m - k$ nonnegative parts (so 0 occurs at most once). As such, $\lambda_{(b)}$ must contain a column of height y . (Recall

that $y < m - k$.) Attaching another such column means that $\lambda'_{(b)}$ still has distinct nonnegative parts. Attaching the ends as above also preserves distinct parts.

Case 2a: Again attaching the column to $\lambda_{(M-b)}$ preserves distinct parts because $z < m - k$. The fact that $M - b - a \neq b - a$ implies that $\lambda'_{(M-b)}$ still does not contain two columns of height y .

Case 2b: Since $\lambda_{(M-b)}$ contains two columns of height y , removing one such column preserves distinct parts.

Cases are separated as follows.

Case 1: $\nu_a > \nu_{M-a}$ and $\lambda_{(a)}$ contains two columns of height y .

Case 2a: $\nu_a > \nu_{M-a}$ and $\lambda_{(a)}$ does not contain two columns of height y .

Case 2b: $\nu_a < \nu_{M-a}$.

This concludes the proof. □

Remark. Unlike in Theorem 2, it appears that the extra factor $(1 + q^{LM+a})$ in the left term of Theorem 3 is often not needed for nonnegativity. A computational search up to $M \leq 12$, $L \leq 20$ and $nM \leq 250$ reveals that for

$$\sum_{m,n \geq 0} d'(m, n) z^m q^n := (-zq^a, -zq^{M-a}; q^M)_L - (-zq^b, -zq^{M-b}; q^M)_L,$$

we have some $d'(m, nM) < 0$ only when $(a, b, M) = (1, 2, 5)$.

In fact, we can condition on more than just 2 columns to prove the following new result.

Proposition 1. *Let $d \geq 0$, $1 \leq a < b < \frac{M}{2}$ and $\gcd(b, M) = 1$. Let $p^{(d)}(n, m, j, A)$ denote the number of partitions of n into m parts congruent to $\pm j \pmod{M}$, whose parts are at most A such that the gap between successive parts is greater than dM . Then for all $n, m \geq 0$,*

$$p^{(d)}(nM, m, a, LM + a) \geq p^{(d)}(nM, m, b, LM - b).$$

If in addition a is odd, then we also have

$$p^{(d)}\left(nM + \frac{M}{2}, m, a, LM + a\right) \geq p^{(d)}\left(nM + \frac{M}{2}, m, b, LM - b\right).$$

Substituting $d = 0$ and $d = 1$ gives Theorems 2 and 3 respectively.

Proof. Let $\lambda = (\lambda_{(b)}, \lambda_{(M-b)}, (b^{\nu_b}, (M-b)^{\nu_{M-b}}))$ be a partition counted by $p^{(d)}(nM, m, b, LM - b)$. Then the M modular diagrams $\lambda_{(b)}$ and $\lambda_{(M-b)}$ are partitions into nonnegative multiples on M such that the difference in successive parts is at least $(d + 1)M$. Our injections $\varphi_k^{(d)}$ are the same as before, except that we condition in cases 2 or 3 on whether or not $\lambda_{(M-b)}$ contains $d + 2$ columns of height y . \square

3. Applications to Kanade-Russell’s Conjectures

In [11], Kanade and Russell conjectured several new Rogers-Ramanujan-type product-sum identities—three arising from the theory of affine Lie algebras, and several companions. Bringmann, Jennings-Shaffer and Mahlburg were able to prove many of these [6], and they reduced the sum-sides of the four conjectures below from triple series to a single series. Here, \mathcal{KR}_j is Identity j in [11], and $H_j(x)$ is the sum side as denoted in [6].

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{KR}_4 : \quad & H_4(1) = \frac{1}{(q, q^4, q^5, q^9, q^{11}; q^{12})_\infty}, \\ \mathcal{KR}_{4a} : \quad & H_5(1) = \frac{1}{(q, q^5, q^7, q^8, q^9; q^{12})_\infty}, \\ \mathcal{KR}_6 : \quad & H_8(1) = \frac{1}{(q, q^3, q^7, q^8, q^{11}; q^{12})_\infty}, \\ \mathcal{KR}_{6a} : \quad & H_9(1) = \frac{1}{(q^3, q^4, q^5, q^7, q^{11}; q^{12})_\infty}. \end{aligned}$$

The pairs of sum-sides, $(H_4(1), H_5(1))$ and $(H_8(1), H_9(1))$, are composed of two generating functions for partitions that satisfy the same set of gap conditions, but H_5 and H_9 have an additional condition on the smallest part (see [11]). Hence, as with the Rogers-Ramanujan sum-sides, we have the inequalities

$$H_4(1) - H_5(1) \succeq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad H_8(1) - H_9(1) \succeq 0,$$

which, if the conjectures are true, imply the following result.

Proposition 2. *The following inequalities hold.*

$$\frac{1}{(q, q^4, q^5, q^9, q^{11}; q^{12})_\infty} - \frac{1}{(q, q^5, q^7, q^8, q^9; q^{12})_\infty} \succeq 0, \tag{3}$$

$$\frac{1}{(q, q^3, q^7, q^8, q^{11}; q^{12})_\infty} - \frac{1}{(q^3, q^4, q^5, q^7, q^{11}; q^{12})_\infty} \succeq 0. \tag{4}$$

Proof. (4) is an immediate consequence of Theorem 1, since for every $L \geq 0$,

$$\frac{1}{(q, q^8; q^{12})_L} - \frac{1}{(q^4, q^5; q^{12})_L} \succeq 0.$$

Multiplying both sides by the positive series $\frac{1}{(q^3, q^7, q^{11}; q^{12})_\infty}$ and taking the limit as $L \rightarrow \infty$ finishes the proof of (4).

Andrews' Anti-telescoping Method [1] works seamlessly to show (3). Define

$$P(j) := (q, q^4, q^{11}; q^{12})_j \quad \text{and} \quad Q(j) := (q, q^7, q^8; q^{12})_j,$$

and note that the following implies (3):

$$\frac{1}{P(L)} - \frac{1}{Q(L)} \succeq 0 \quad \text{for all } L \geq 0. \tag{5}$$

Now we write

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{P(L)} - \frac{1}{Q(L)} &= \frac{1}{Q(L)} \left(\frac{Q(L)}{P(L)} - 1 \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{Q(L)} \sum_{j=1}^L \left(\frac{Q(j)}{P(j)} - \frac{Q(j-1)}{P(j-1)} \right) \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^L \frac{1}{\frac{Q(L)}{Q(j-1)} P(j)} \left(\frac{Q(j)}{Q(j-1)} - \frac{P(j)}{P(j-1)} \right), \end{aligned}$$

whose j -th term is

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{(1 - q^{12j-11})q^{12(j-1)}}{(q^{12j-11}, q^{12j-5}, q^{12j-4}; q^{12})_{L-j+1}(q, q^4, q^{11}; q^{12})_j} \times (-q^7 - q^8 + q^4 + q^{11}) \\ &= \frac{(1 - q^{12j-11})q^{12(j-1)}}{(q^{12j-11}, q^{12j-5}, q^{12j-4}; q^{12})_{L-j+1}(q, q^4, q^{11}; q^{12})_j} \times q^4(1 - q^3)(1 - q^4). \tag{6} \end{aligned}$$

The terms $(1 - q^4)$ and $(1 - q^{12j-11})$ are cancelled in the denominator, and we can write $\frac{1-q^3}{1-q} = 1 + q + q^2$. Hence, (6) is nonnegative for every j , proving (5) and then (3). \square

Another pair of identities in [11] with an Ehrenpreis Problem set-up is the following.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{KR}_5 : \quad & H_6(1) = \frac{1}{(q^2; q^4)_\infty} \prod_{n \geq 0} \left(1 + q^{4n+1} + q^{2(4n+1)} \right), \\ \mathcal{KR}_{5a} : \quad & H_7(1) = \frac{1}{(q^2; q^4)_\infty} \prod_{n \geq 0} \left(1 + q^{4n+3} + q^{2(4n+3)} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Both identities were proved in [6], and there is an obvious injection proving

$$\frac{1}{(q^2; q^4)_\infty} \prod_{n \geq 0} (1 + q^{4n+1} + q^{2(4n+1)}) - \frac{1}{(q^2; q^4)_\infty} \prod_{n \geq 0} (1 + q^{4n+3} + q^{2(4n+3)}) \geq 0,$$

namely, sending each $(4n + 3)$ to the pair $(4n + 1, 2)$.

Finally, we discuss the Ehrenpreis problems among \mathcal{KR}_1 , \mathcal{KR}_2 and \mathcal{KR}_3 . These were proved in [6], and their respective sum-sides were denoted $H_1(x)$, $H_2(x)$ and $H_3(x)$. Using the methods of [11], we have found slightly different conditions for the partitions enumerated on the sum-side:

1. No consecutive parts are allowed.
2. Odd parts do not repeat.
3. Even parts appear at most twice.
4. We have $(\lambda_j, \lambda_{j+1}, \lambda_{j+2}) \notin \{(2k, 2k, 2k+2), (2k, 2k, 2k+3), (2k+1, 2k+3, 2k+5), (2k-2, 2k, 2k)\}$ for any j and k .³

Note that our fourth condition is changed slightly from Kanade and Russell’s in [11], page 5. The sum-side of \mathcal{KR}_2 has the further restriction that the part 1 may not appear, and in the sum-side of \mathcal{KR}_3 , the parts 1, 2 and 3 may not appear. Hence, $H_1(1) \geq H_2(1) \geq H_3(1)$ and it follows from Theorem 1.1 of [6] that

$$\frac{1}{(q, q^4, q^6, q^8, q^{11}; q^{12})_\infty} \geq \frac{(-q^3, -q^9; q^{12})_\infty}{(q^2, q^4, q^8, q^{10}; q^{12})_\infty} \geq \frac{1}{(q^4, q^5, q^6, q^7, q^8; q^{12})_\infty}.$$

The inequality between the far left and right products is a consequence of Theorem 5.3 of [4], but a direct proof of the other two inequalities remains open.

4. Concluding Remarks

As we pointed out in the introduction, (1) was the start of Andrews-Baxter’s “motivated” proof of the Rogers-Ramanujan identities [2]. They defined $G_1 := (q, q^4; q^5)_\infty^{-1}$ and $G_2 := (q^2, q^3; q^5)_\infty^{-1}$, and then recursively

$$G_i := \frac{G_{i-2} - G_{i-1}}{q^{i-2}}, \quad \text{for } i \geq 3. \tag{7}$$

They then observed computationally that $G_i = 1 + \sum_{n \geq i} g_{i,n} q^n \geq 0$. Thus, as $i \rightarrow \infty$ the coefficient of q^n in G_i is eventually 0. This was their “Empirical Hypothesis,” and proving it leads easily to a new proof of the Rogers-Ramanujan identities.

³As in [11], we have written parts in increasing order.

Note that, starting from the sum-sides of G_1 and G_2 , the recursive definition (7) and the Empirical Hypothesis are completely natural. For example, if \mathcal{RR} denotes the set of gap-2 partitions, then by the Rogers-Ramanujan Identities,

$$G_1 - G_2 = \sum_{\substack{\lambda \in \mathcal{RR} \\ \lambda_1 \geq 1}} q^{|\lambda|} = q \left(1 + \sum_{\substack{\lambda \in \mathcal{RR} \\ \lambda_j \geq 3}} q^{|\lambda|} \right),$$

and so

$$G_2 - G_3 = \sum_{\substack{\lambda \in \mathcal{RR} \\ \lambda_j \geq 2 \\ \lambda_j \geq 2}} q^{|\lambda|} = q^2 \left(1 + \sum_{\substack{\lambda \in \mathcal{RR} \\ \lambda_j \geq 4}} q^{|\lambda|} \right),$$

and so on.

For \mathcal{KR}_4 , \mathcal{KR}_{4a} , \mathcal{KR}_6 and \mathcal{KR}_{6a} , we can expect the more complicated conditions on the sum-sides to lead to more complicated recurrences. For example, the recurrence below was shown for \mathcal{KR}_4 ([6], equation 4.2).

$$H_4(x) = (1 + xq)H_4(xq^2) + xq^2(1 + xq^3)H_4(xq^4) + x^2q^6(1 - xq^4)H_4(xq^6).$$

Combinatorial proofs of the above and the similar recurrences in [6] may give insight into an ‘‘Empirical Hypothesis’’ for \mathcal{KR}_4 , \mathcal{KR}_{4a} , \mathcal{KR}_6 and \mathcal{KR}_{6a} . Indeed, the techniques for ‘‘motivated proofs’’ have been expanded to accommodate identities with gap-conditions more complicated than those of \mathcal{RR} , notably in [7], [9] and [12]. Perhaps further developments will give an answer to the following question: Do there exist ‘‘motivated proofs’’ of \mathcal{KR}_4 , \mathcal{KR}_{4a} , \mathcal{KR}_6 and \mathcal{KR}_{6a} ?

This would be especially interesting, since to our knowledge there have not yet been ‘‘motivated proofs’’ featuring asymmetric products.

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